

**Extractive Spectrophotometric Method for the
Determination of Iron(III) in Green Leafy
Vegetables using Sodium Pentamethylene
Dithiocarbamate**

K. SARASWATHI*, M. DASARATHA RAMAIAH

and

V. V. RAMANA

Department of Chemistry, S. V. University College,
Tirupati-517 502

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IN continuation of our earlier work on metal complexes of sodium pentamethylene dithiocarbamates¹, we report herein a simple and sensitive spectrophotometric procedure for the determination of Fe^{III}. Since sodium pentamethylene dithiocarbamate (Pipdte) has been widely used for the determination of many metal ions a procedure is adopted for the determination of iron in the leaves of *Amaranthus viridis* and *A. gangeticus*.

Experimental

Na(Pipdte) was prepared and recrystallised from benzene² and 1% of stock solution was prepared in double-distilled water.

Ferric ammonium sulphate (Proanalysis) dissolved in 2M H₂SO₄ was diluted with double-distilled water. All other chemicals were of A.R. grade.

Absorbance measurements were made using a Shimadzu PR-1 spectrophotometer and pH adjustments made on an Elico LI-10 pH meter.

A 0.25 × 10⁻³ M Fe^{III} solution (1 ml), a buffer of pH ~4.2 (1 ml), salting-out agent (0.1 M MgSO₄, 1 ml), 1% Pipdte (1 ml), water (6 ml) and CHCl₃ (10 ml) were mixed in the above order and the organic layer containing the complex was separated. The extraction of the water-insoluble yellowish green complex into CHCl₃ was stable for 6 h. Quantitative extraction could be achieved in a single extraction and within 2 min of shaking in the presence of magnesium sulphate. The complex showed an absorption maximum at 350 nm. Neither the reagent nor the metal ion had any absorbance in the range of study.

Results and Discussion

The metal chelate showed maximum absorbance in the pH range 3–6 in sodium acetate and acetic acid buffer. The pH of 4.2 is selected to eliminate the interference of some metal ions like Al^{III} and Zn^{II}. At least a six-fold excess of the reagent is necessary for consistency in absorbance. Quantitative determination of iron is possible in the range 1–15 ppm of Fe^{III} per 10 ml of the organic layer. The molar absorptivity of the complex and sensitivity

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are found to be $1.96 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.02 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

Job's method, mole-ratio method and Asmus method were employed to obtain the composition of the complex and the ratio of metal-to-ligand was found to be 1 : 3. The instability constant as calculated from Edmond and Birnbaum method and Asmus method was found to be 2.0×10^{-9} .

The ions, Sn^{II} , W^{VI} , Sr^{II} , Al^{III} , Zn^{II} , sulphate, carbonate, nitrate, fluoride, chloride, bromide, oxalate, phosphate, tartrate do not interfere. However, the interference of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} can be masked with 2% KCN and that of Mo^{VI} by 1% fluoride solution. Nitrite, iodate, bromate and periodate ions interfere in the determination.

Application : The procedure was applied for the determination of Fe^{III} in the leaves of *A. viridis* and *A. gangeticus* and the results obtained (in mg/100 g) are comparable to that by the phenanthroline method³ (shown in the parenthesis) : 18.70 (18.46), 26.64 (26.58).

The present method for the estimation of Fe^{III} in the leaves is simple, less time-consuming and free from interference of other metal ions.

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